

Can teachers' digital competence influence technology acceptance in vocational education?

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Technology acceptance model
Teachers' digital competence belief
Vocational education

ABSTRACT

Acceptance of technology in educational contexts is a relevant factor in determining teachers' intention to use digital tools in their teaching practice. However, the mechanism through which teachers' digital competence can influence or enhance their technology acceptance and use intention remains relatively unexplored, especially in the context of vocational education and training. The aim of this study is twofold: to evaluate the fit of the technology acceptance model (TAM) in the context of vocational education, and to examine the relationship between self-assessed teachers' digital competence belief and their acceptance of and intention to use technology in their classroom. Data were collected via a self-administered questionnaire and the responses of 2011 vocational teachers were analysed. Applying structural equation modelling, the results show that the TAM adequately explains teachers' intention to use digital tools in vocational education; further, there are positive and significant relationships between teachers' beliefs about their digital competence and their beliefs about technology ease of use and the perceived usefulness of technology in teaching; this latter, positively correlates with technology use intention. Understanding the factors interplaying with teachers' acceptance of technology and use intention is important for designing teacher training to enhance the successful integration of technology and to foster the connectivity between the different learning locations of vocational education.

1. Introduction

In the last two decades, different technologies have become more available and accessible for teachers, and new digital tools and instructional materials have been developed to support teaching and learning; consequently, governmental initiatives and training programs around the world have been presented to facilitate the introduction of technology in education and to encourage the process of digitalisation in schools (e.g., see the Lifelong Learning Strategy in Estonia 2020 [2014], the Good School Reform in Italy [2015], and Finland's curriculum reform [2016]). However, while the availability of hardware and software for education is widespread, the use of these digital tools in the teaching practice, as well as digital competence in general, is still uneven among teachers. The [International Computer and Information Literacy Study \(2018\)](#) documented that less than 50% of teachers used technologies frequently in their teaching ([Fraillon et al., 2019](#), p. 74). The results of the 2018 OECD Teaching and Learning International Survey revealed that teachers reported a high need for training for technology-related skills and that only 43% of teachers felt prepared to use technology in

teaching ([OECD, 2019](#)). Even despite the increasing adoption of technology in education forced by the COVID-19 emergency, teachers from 64 different countries around the world showed heterogeneity with respect to their readiness to use technology in teaching ([Scherer et al., 2021](#)).

Many studies have sought to understand the factors that influence teachers' use of technology in education, revealing that multiple factors interplay at different levels (e.g., educational systems, schools, teachers). The model of *contextual facilitators for learning activities involving technology* (Cb - model) proposed by [Sailer et al. \(2021\)](#) gives an overview of the complex dynamic of factors influencing technology use in education identifying also the relationships between the school- and teachers-related factors interweaving.

The educational system can provide support and essential resources necessary to develop the digital competence of school staff ([Krumsvik et al., 2016](#)). Although a school's support for technology integration is relevant, it is not determinant of technology use in classroom. For example, a recent study identified some teachers who perceived a high level of institutional support for online teaching and learning, but a low

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rating of self-efficacy in using technology (Scherer et al., 2021). Thus, even though their school's support was appropriate, the teachers' own beliefs about their competencies still worked as barriers to their use of technology. At the school level, the availability of and access to digital tools (e.g., school infrastructure, computers for instruction, and internet access) and the quality of the digital infrastructure are necessary prerequisites, but they are not sufficient conditions alone to lead teachers toward using technology in their classrooms (Bingimlas, 2009). The availability of the infrastructure only partially explains the use of technology by teachers (Drossel & Eickelmann, 2017). Several studies have found that teachers' individual characteristics—such as their beliefs, attitudes, motivations, and perceived self-efficacy—have much greater weight in explaining technology use in schools than the amount of and access to technological infrastructure (Backfisch et al., 2021; Gil-Flores et al., 2017; Tondeur et al., 2008; Valtonen et al., 2015). Furthermore, also the Cb - model acknowledges the importance of teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in influencing teachers' digital technology use (Sailer et al., 2021).

According to the technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989), teachers' beliefs regarding the ease of use and usefulness of technology, and their own attitudes toward technology are the most critical factors influencing their acceptance of technology and their consequent intention to use it. Although its genesis is not directly connected to education, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a promising and widely used model to explain teachers' intention to use technology, and it has been applied to different technologies in a variety of contexts. However, a recent meta-analysis by Scherer and Teo (2019) highlights that the findings from previous studies that explored the role of technology acceptance in education and that specifically referenced the TAM were contradictory. Different relation patterns between the TAM variables were found and the variance of the outcome variable (i.e., use intention) explained by the model varies from 3% to 90% across studies. In addition, there is a gap in the research on teachers' technology acceptance in the context of vocational education and training that needs to be addressed. In vocational schools, digital technologies play an important role in bridging the gap between what is taught in the classroom and what students experience in the workplace where they undertake their apprenticeship (Schwendimann et al., 2015). Indeed, vocational teachers need to be aware of the activities their students are involved in and the skills they are trained for at the workplace in order to adapt their classroom teaching to connect theory and practice (Kyndt et al., 2022). The 'connectivity' between theoretical knowledge and practical skills is crucial for reflective learning; digital technologies are a very useful means for fostering this communication and connection between the two locations, in both directions (Cattaneo et al., 2022). Hence, vocational teachers, in addition to the digital competences of educators as described by the Digital Competence Framework of Educators (Dig-CompEdu; Redecker, 2017), should have the digital competences necessary to handle technological devices essential for connectivity.

Further extensions of the TAM have been proposed to understand which external variables intertwine with perceived ease of use, usefulness, and attitude toward technology in influencing technology use intention (e.g., TAM 2 by Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) by Venkatesh et al., 2003). Among these other variables, self-efficacy belief, which concerns one's judgment of how well they can execute certain actions, is worth interest (Ajzen, 1991; Bandura, 1977). A person's belief in their ability to perform a target behaviour strongly influences their choice, preparation, and effort expended to engage in the behaviour (Bandura, 1977). In the context of technology use for education, teachers' self-efficacy belief (or behavioural control) related to technology use in teaching could be operationalised as the belief of their own competence in using technology for teaching and learning (i.e., Teachers' Digital Competence Beliefs, TDCB). To the best of our knowledge, little empirical research has focused on the relationship between the TAM and TDCB.

On this basis, the aim of the present study is twofold: first, we

investigate whether the TAM is applicable in the context of vocational education; then, we explore the relation between TDCB and technology acceptance in education to better understand the factors intertwined with teachers' intention to use technology in their practice. The significance of the present study is to identify the antecedents of technology acceptance at the teachers' level to address interventions and design training courses that will motivate and heighten the use of technology by teachers active in vocational education. Before presenting the study in detail, we review previous research on the TAM, its relationship with TDCB and we present the specificities of vocational education.

1.1. The technology acceptance model (TAM) in education

Based on the theory of reasoned action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975), a general model for the understanding of human behaviour, the TAM was introduced by Fred D. Davis in 1989 to predict the acceptance of a technology system. The purpose of the model was to understand the determinants of employees' acceptance of technology and adoption of it in the workplace. In the model proposed by Davis et al. (1989), the core TAM variables explaining the acceptance of technology are: 1) *Perceived Usefulness* (PU), i.e., the degree to which a person believes that the use of technology would enhance their job performance; 2) *Perceived Ease of Use* (PEU), i.e., the belief that the use of technology is effortless and easy; 3) *Attitude Towards Technology* (ATT), i.e., the overall evaluation of technology characterised by positive or negative feelings toward using it. In the original TAM, PEU directly affects PU: the more a technology is perceived as easy to use, the more it is likely to be used. ATT is determined jointly by both PU and PEU, and it directly influences the *behavioural intention* (BI), i.e., the intention of using technology in one's professional activity; in turn, the BI would lead to effective technology adoption (and then practical, applied use). ATT has a mediating role between beliefs on technology (i.e., PU and PEU) and the BI. The first version of TAM introduced by Davis was revised in later years. The modification of TAM by Venkatesh and Davis (1996) excluded the attitude construct, based on empirical evidence, because it did not fully mediate the effect of PEU and PU on intention. Thus, PEU and PU have a direct influence on BI as shown in Fig. 1.

Due to the limitations of the TAM in terms of explanatory power, a second model (TAM 2) was developed (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), based on the assumption that job goals and consequences of using technology serve as a basis for PU. Since TAM 2 only focused on the determinants of PU, Venkatesh and Bala (2008) further integrated the determining factors of PEU in the model, proposing TAM 3. The authors included individual differences, system characteristics, social influence, and facilitating conditions as determinants of PEU and PU. Experience was added to the TAM 3 as a moderator of the relationship between computer anxiety and PEU, PEU and PU, PEU and BI. Finally, Venkatesh et al. (2003) presented the UTAUT with performance expectancy (formed by perceived usefulness, extrinsic motivation, job-fit, relative advantage, and outcome expectations), effort expectancy (formed by perceived ease of use and complexity), social influence, and facilitating

Fig. 1. Technology acceptance model (Davis & Venkatesh, 1996). Note. PU = perceived usefulness; PEU = perceived ease of use; BI = behavioural intention; AU = actual use.

conditions as the four key determinants of BI.

Over the years, the original model that only focused on cognitive aspects was extended with the addition of emotional, motivational, and contextual variables. However, Venkatesh et al. (2003) found that social influence was not significant in voluntary contexts and that PU is the variable that has the highest influence on one's intention to use technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Therefore, investigating the key predictors of PU is a worthy pursuit.

Despite the fact that the original TAM (1996) is more parsimonious than its extensions and it omits important variables and processes, referring to the core but, at the same time, the widely validated TAM is suitable for the preliminary exploration of its relationship with other variables in new settings.

Over the past three decades, there has been empirical support in favour of the TAM; indeed, it has been revealed to be a concise and powerful model to explain technology acceptance. It is broadly applicable to different technologies and settings, and it has been extensively used in the context of education to determine teachers' intention of using technologies in their educational practice (Marangunic & Granic, 2015).

Despite the large number of empirical studies that have tested the validity of the TAM among different samples of teachers, the two meta-analyses by Scherer and colleagues (Scherer & Teo, 2019; Scherer et al., 2019), combining the results from previous research on the TAM in education, highlighted differences in structural parameters within the TAM across studies. Differences were reported in the statistical significance of path coefficients, in the variance explained in the intention to use technology, and in moderation effects. For example, the statistical significance of the effect of PEU on PU was not supported by every study; some studies found that PU was a stronger predictor of positive attitude than PEU, while in other studies it was exactly the opposite. The inconsistency of these findings could have been caused by differing characteristics between the samples examined, which can act as moderators on the relations between the TAM variables. For instance, the effect of PEU on ATT was larger for pre-service teachers than in-service teachers (Scherer & Teo, 2019), suggesting that the variance of the effects of PEU on ATT is affected by the level of educational experience (i. e., years of teaching).

Such different findings suggest that the TAM still demands further investigation; an assessment of its goodness of fit is recommended in particular, taking into account the specific research context. In fact, some studies that have investigated the structural invariance of the TAM across different groups of teachers (e. g., pre- and in-services teachers, or teachers from different nationalities) oftentimes did not identify full invariance across groups, suggesting that the TAM may not fully apply to all contexts to the same extent, and that the context can play an important role (Scherer et al., 2019).

These final points brought us to consider the relevance of a study within vocational education context. There are few studies investigating teachers' technology acceptance in the context of vocational education and training (Zarafshani et al., 2020), despite the high relevance that technology integration assumes in this specific setting (e. g., Schwendimann, et al., 2015; UNESCO, 2020). In addition, investigating the TAM and applying it to a new context in vocational education would constitute a further step towards validation of the model.

In the next paragraph we briefly present the characteristics of the vocational education system, highlighting its specific peculiarities and the role digital technologies can play within it.

1.2. The Swiss vocational education and training system

In most cases, vocational education and training (VET) is built upon the alternation between theory and practice, providing learners with the knowledge and skills needed to become a professional. In Switzerland, the VET system is also mainly characterized by a dual track, where the learners alternate between vocational school and the company where

they practice as apprentices. At school, the apprentices acquire general (e. g., communication, language, civic education) and professional knowledge. At the workplace, they face real-life situations, practice professional activities under the supervision of an expert trainer and develop professional competences. In addition to this basic alternation, Swiss vocational curricula also integrate branch courses that often take place in training centres led by corporate associations, thus completing the apprentices' training (for more details on the Swiss VET system, see Bonoli et al., 2018; Strahm et al., 2016). As a result, learning emerges from the interaction of different contexts and, depending on the location, apprentices interact with different educators, such as teachers, trainers or instructors. This often leads learners to perceive gaps between what they learn at school and what they practice at the workplace, that is, the abstract explicit knowledge typically addressed at school and the procedural implicit knowledge they face at the workplace (e. g., Schaap et al., 2012). Given this gap between the dual contexts, technologies can be exploited to 'bridge the gap' between the school and the workplace, providing support to connect and integrate the knowledge derived from each learning location (Cattaneo & Aprea, 2018; Schwendimann et al., 2015). Indeed, thanks to digital technology, teachers in schools can communicate and collaborate with in-company trainers and can be informed about the activities their learners perform when they are not at school, thus bringing the professional experiences to the school. In addition, technologies can create a specific space for reflection where different knowledge and experiences can be integrated, reflected upon, and shared with all the actors involved.

To conclude, apart from other more general aims that teachers pursue when integrating technologies in their teaching, in vocational schools, the use of technology by teachers is essential for fostering the connectivity between the VET learning locations. To exploit opportunities provided by technologies requires high levels of teacher competence in using digital devices and software in their teaching practice at school.

Another important remark is worth making at this point. We have already elaborated on the different educator profiles in the Swiss VET system, based on the locations they are active in (teachers at school, in-company trainers, branch course instructors). These three figures overlap with the five vocational teachers' profiles generally distinguished in the literature: people working in formal school or college settings; people acting as instructors working in school settings, particularly in vocational laboratories; people working in companies with the responsibility of training apprentices as a part of their job functions; people working in labour market training institutions supported by public authorities; and people working in organizations managed by employers' organizations or corporate associations (Grollmann, 2008). In our study, we only focused on schools and, therefore, on vocational teachers who are active in secondary schools and VET colleges. The digital competences they need are similar to those of the teachers in general education, with the exception of the additional competence they need for using technology to exploit connectivity.

1.3. Teachers' digital competence belief (TDCB) as a predictor of technology acceptance

In recent years, several efforts have been made to define the digital competence needed for teachers to use technology in the classroom (From, 2017; Krumsvik, 2009; Krumsvik et al., 2016); however, there is still some confusion regarding what digital competence means. In general, it refers to the ability to use information and communication technologies, such as digital tools or software (From, 2017). However, digital competence of teachers is more complex to define; it is a broader concept that includes not only the technical skills of using technological devices and digital resources in an educational context, but it also considers the pedagogical dimension, attitude, strategies, and awareness that enables teachers using technology to achieve teaching and learning goals effectively (Cattaneo et al., 2022; Hämäläinen et al., 2021;

Reisoğlu & Çebi, 2020).

Some frameworks have been proposed to describe the multiple facets of digital competencies of teachers (Zhao et al., 2021). Among these, the European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu) considers digital competence as the ability to make safe, critical, and creative use of technology to enrich teaching and learning objectives (Redecker, 2017). DigCompEdu maintains a tight focus on pedagogy and provides details on the pedagogical use of technology applicable to all educational subjects in different educational contexts, in an ever-changing technological landscape. The framework identifies 22 specific digital competencies of educators, categorised into the following six areas: 1) professional engagement, 2) digital resources, 3) teaching and learning, 4) assessment, 5) empowering learners, and 6) facilitating learners' digital competence. Teachers evaluate their digital competencies through a self-assessment tool which provides detailed feedback on personal strengths and weaknesses and enables a process of self-reflection useful for professional development.

However, when assessing competence, self-reporting techniques are problematic because the participants' ability to accurately assess what they can do or know is a limitation for the accuracy of responses collected (Brantley-Dias & Ertmer, 2013). The survey results represent the teachers' belief about their competence rather than their actual level of competence. This latter should be measured by performance tasks (Guardia et al., 2017). Thus, the operationalization of digital competence via the DigCompEdu self-assessment tool encompasses the individuals' belief of their mastering the competence to use educational technologies, design teaching and accomplish instructional objectives using technological tools effectively; this operationalization is closely related to the construct of perceived self-efficacy with regard to the use of technologies in education.

As self-efficacy is defined as the individual's beliefs in the personal capability to organize the course of action to complete a task successfully and to achieve specific goals (Bandura, 1977), the self-assessed digital competence would overlap with the construct of perceived self-efficacy in relation to the use of digital technology. According to Bandura's theory, behaviour depends on both self-efficacy beliefs and outcome expectation: if people perceive themselves as being able to perform an action successfully, and believe that their action will have positive results, they are much more likely to be motivated to perform that action. Thus, the concept of self-efficacy belief was integrated in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) as the perceived behaviour control variable affecting one's behavioural intention. Therefore, in line with this theoretical background, the teachers' self-evaluation of their digital competence – that we labelled as Teachers' Digital Competence Belief, TDCB – might interweave with their beliefs on technology use and influence their behavioural intention of using technology for teaching and learning. However, whether TDCB directly or indirectly affects the intention to use technology in teaching is still not clear (Backfisch et al., 2021). Scherer et al. (2019) hypothesised a *cascade mechanism*, according to which self-efficacy beliefs were linked to the TAM variables and, in turn, utility beliefs were linked to behavioural intention. Evidence from previous studies supports this argument (Abdullah & Ward, 2016; Sánchez-Prieto et al., 2017). Literature shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between perceived computer competence, attitude towards computer-assisted education, and intention to use technology (Baturay et al., 2017); Wong et al. (2012) have found that teachers' self-assessed capability to teach with computers significantly and positively influences ATT, PEU, and PU, and has an indirect positive effect on their behavioural intention to use computers. Backfisch et al. (2021) found that teachers' skills and knowledge to successfully integrate technologies into teaching (measured by TPACK self-efficacy) influences their actual use of technology both directly and indirectly through its influence on the perceived usefulness of technology.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no studies until now have explored the relationship between the digital competence belief of

teachers and their technology acceptance in vocational education. Thus, based on the previously examined literature, we hypothesize that TDCB significantly correlates with the PEU and PU, that in turn is positively related to the intention of using digital tools in teaching. We also hypothesize a direct association between TDCB and BI. Linking TDCB with the TAM could shed more light on the process of technology acceptance and use by vocational teachers and reinforce the status and acceptance of the TAM in the education field. Furthermore, exploring the relationship between TDCB, PEU, PU and BI could guide the design of vocational teachers' training to motivate teachers to use technology in their teaching.

1.4. Aim and hypotheses

Grounded in the review of the existing literature on the TAM and teachers' digital competence, our study aimed (1) to evaluate whether the TAM applies to the context of vocational education in predicting teachers' intention to use technology, and (2) to investigate the relationship between teachers' self-assessed digital competence (i.e., TDCB), their beliefs about technology (i.e., PEU and PU) and their intention to use it. Hence, our research questions were as follow:

RQ1) To what extent does the TAM explain teachers' intention to use technology in vocational education?

RQ2) What is the relationship between TDCB and teachers' technology acceptance?

In accordance with our research questions, we proposed the following research hypotheses:

H1. All the paths between PU, PEU, and BI are positive and statistically significant in accordance with the original TAM.

H2. TDCB has a positive and significant relationship with PU, PEU, and BI.

The hypothesised relationships between the TAM variables and TDCB are summarised in Fig. 2. All the displayed paths were hypothesised to be significant and positive.

2. Methods

2.1. Procedure and sample

Data were collected through an online survey completed voluntarily by teachers from Swiss vocational schools between June and September 2020. After receiving permission from the Education Administration, a link to the online questionnaire was sent to all vocational institutions requesting that the school management forward the link to teachers. All participants were informed of the study's aim, and their anonymity was guaranteed. We collected 3404 responses; 972 of them were excluded from the analyses when the questionnaire's completion was less than 100% to avoid missing values in the analytical sample. After data cleaning (e.g., removal of duplicates and outliers), the final analytical sample included 2011 teachers.

Among the participants, 43.6% were women (n = 876), 44.2% were

Fig. 2. Hypothesised model. Note. TDC = Teachers' Digital Competence Belief; PU = Perceived Usefulness; PEU = Perceived Ease of Use; BI = Behavioural Intention.

men (n = 888) and the remainder did not report information on gender. All demographic information about the sample is reported in Table 1.

2.2. Measures

TAM variables. Six items developed by Venkatesh et al. (2003) were adapted to measure technology usefulness (PU) and ease of use (PEU) as perceived by the teachers in the sample. Response options ranged from *Absolutely disagree* (1) to *Absolutely agree* (6). Items were averaged to compound the PU and PEU. A higher level of agreement in the responses corresponds to more positive beliefs about technology use for teaching and learning.

Behavioural intention. On a scale from 1 to 6, the teachers reported their level of agreement with two statements regarding their intention to use technology in their future teaching practice. The two items were inspired by Venkatesh et al. (2003) and a higher level of agreement in the responses corresponds to a greater intention to use technology.

Teachers' Digital Competence Belief. Based on the European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (see DigCompEdu2.0 in Redecker, 2017), to assess TDCB we used a 22-item scale (see also Lucas et al., 2021) distributed over the following six dimensions: professional engagement, digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment, empowering learners, and facilitating learners' digital competence. In addition, we developed seven items specific to the VET context to assess the teachers' competence beliefs in using technology to foster the connectivity between learning locations. The new items are theoretically associated to the following dimensions of the TDCB scale: professional engagement, teaching and learning, and facilitating learners' digital competence. Teachers rated their beliefs about their level of competence for each item on a five-point Likert scale from *Not at all competent* (0) to *Highly competent* (4). Since the digital competence scale is based on self-reported assessment, we considered this as a measure of the teachers' beliefs about their competence in using technology efficiently in their teaching practice. The sum of the responses to these 29 items created a TDCB total score ranging from 0 to 116.

The survey's items are reported in Appendix A.

2.3. Data analysis

First, descriptive statistics for all measures were calculated. The univariate and multivariate normality were evaluated following the recommendation by Kline (2016). Bivariate correlation analysis for all study variables as well as gender, age, and teaching experience (i.e., years of teaching) were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics (version 27)

Table 1
Analytical sample information.

Gender	N	%
Male	888	44.2
Female	876	43.6
Prefer not to say	247	12.3
Age range (years)		
< 30	56	2.8
30–39	341	17.0
40–49	582	28.9
50–59	658	32.7
≥ 60	162	8.1
Prefer not to say	212	10.5
Teaching experience (years)		
1–3	212	10.5
4–5	152	7.6
6–9	252	12.5
10–14	396	19.7
15–19	258	12.8
20–24	237	11.8
≥ 25	283	14.1
Prefer not to say	124	6.2

Note. N = number of respondents; % = percentage of respondents.

predictive analytics software to check whether these demographic variables were associated with the TAM. A structural equation modelling approach was used to test our research hypotheses using lavaan package (0.6–7) in R (4.0.2). To test the first hypothesis, we assessed the path coefficients between PU, PEU, and BI on a sample of vocational teachers. We conducted a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) assessing the validity of the TDCB scale to ensure the reliability of further analyses. According to the DigCompEdu framework we assumed that the overall digital competence (second-order factor) comprises six areas of competencies (as first-order factors) which are directly measured by the 22 items. To consider the specificities of VET context, we added two newly developed items in area 1) 'professional engagement' and 3) 'teaching and learning', and three items in area 6) 'facilitating learners' digital competence' and we tested the structure of the final 29-item TDCB scale.

Then, we added the TDCB variable as an antecedent of the original TAM to test the second research hypothesis. The direct effects of TDCB on PU, PEU, and BI were examined. Since the ratio between the number of cases in the final analytical sample (= 2011) and the number of estimated parameters (= 131) to test the hypothesised model through a structural equation model analysis has to be at least 10:1 (Kline, 2016; Schreiber et al., 2006), the analytical sample size was sufficient to obtain reliable results.

We used modification indices to add cross-correlations between items if they were plausible within the hypothetical model. The models' fit was evaluated based on the thresholds recommended by Byrne (2016) for the χ^2 statistics ($p > .05$), comparative fit index (CFI; acceptable fit $>.90$, good fit >0.95), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI; acceptable fit $>.90$), root-mean-square error of estimation (RMSEA; acceptable fit $<.08$, good fit <0.05), and the standardised root-mean-square residual (SRMR <0.05).

3. Results

3.1. Measurement reliability

Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and Cronbach's alpha (α) of the TAM variables are reported in Table 2. Alpha values $> .70$ were considered as acceptable (Nunnally, 1978). Pearson's correlation coefficient is reported for BI measured by two items only.

The mean of the TDCB total score is 86.48 (SD = 19.74). Because the digital competence belief scale is hierarchically structured and alpha coefficients may misestimate the reliability of the total scale score (Black et al., 2015), a second-order confirmatory factor analysis was used to test the validity of the *a priori* defined six-factor structure of the TDCB scale. Following the modification indices, few residual correlations between items, and a correlation between areas 1 and 2 ($r = 0.859, p < .001$) were added. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis showed a good fit to a six-factor model ($\chi^2(342) = 1494.878, p < .001, RMSEA = 0.045, CFI = 0.958, TLI = 0.951, SRMR = 0.033$) and confirmed the structure of the 29-items digital competence scale specific for VET teachers. Results are presented in Table 3. Following the guideline stating that factor loadings <0.40 are weak and factor loadings ≥ 0.60 are strong (Garson, 2010), all items load well on their intended factors.

Table 2
TAM variables information.

	M	SD	α
PU	3.86	1.10	.805
PEU	4.23	1.20	.938
BI	4.38,	1.20	$r = .578, p < .001$

Note. PU = Perceived Usefulness; PEU = Perceived Ease of Use; BI = Behavioural Intention. M = mean; SD = standard deviation; α = Cronbach's alpha; r = Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Table 3
Confirmatory factor analysis results of digital competence belief scale.

	λ
Area 1: Professional Engagement	
I use digital technologies to communicate with learners and colleagues.	.724***
I use digital technologies to collaborate with colleagues, also from other schools.	.661***
I am proactive in developing my skills in the use of digital technologies for teaching.	.781***
I participate in training opportunities through technology.	.781***
<i>I use digital technologies to communicate with other VET actors (e.g., trainers, instructors of inter-company courses).</i>	.606***
<i>I use digital technologies to collaborate with other VET actors (e.g., trainers, instructors of inter-company courses).</i>	.634***
Area 2: Digital Resources	
I use the Web to find and select different digital resources	.698***
I adapt and modify selected digital resources based on relevant criteria.	.827***
I protect sensitive school and learners' data.	.507***
Area 3: Teaching and Learning	
I think carefully about how, when and why to use digital technologies in the classroom, making sure that they are used for the benefit of the learning process.	.626***
I monitor and moderate the activities and interactions of learners in the digital collaborative environments we use at school	.759***
I teach learners to use digital technologies in collaborative processes and group work for the joint construction and creation of resources, knowledge and content.	.802***
I integrate digital tools into my teaching that help learners to plan, monitor and reflect on their own learning.	.728***
<i>I use digital technologies to facilitate the connection between learning places.</i>	.616***
<i>I use digital technologies to foster the connection between theory and practice, the abstract and the concrete, the general and the specific.</i>	.768***
Area 4: Assessment	
I use digital assessment tools to monitor learners' progress.	.795***
I analyze all the data I have available to identify which learners may need further support.	.739***
I use digital technologies to provide effective feedback to learners.	.803***
Area 5: Empowering Learners	
I consider any practical or technical difficulties when making deliveries for learners.	.606***
I use digital technologies to offer learners personalized and differentiated learning opportunities.	.759***
I use digital technologies in my teaching practice to stimulate learners and actively engage them.	.762***
Area 6: Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	
I teach learners criteria and strategies for assessing the reliability of information gathered online and for identifying fabricated, misleading, or distorted information.	.609***
I prepare deliverables that require learners to use digital tools to communicate and collaborate with each other.	.741***
I prepare deliverables that involve the creation of digital content by learners.	.769***
I teach learners to use digital technologies safely and responsibly.	.743***
I encourage learners to use digital technologies creatively to solve concrete problems.	.787***
<i>I use technology to support learners in developing their learning and performance documentation.</i>	.750***
<i>I prepare deliverables that foresee the use of digital tools by learners to communicate and collaborate with external audiences, in particular with their trainer(s) in the company.</i>	.618***
<i>I ask learners to use digital technologies to inform me about their professional practice.</i>	.646***
Teachers Digital Competence (second order)	
Area 1: Professional Engagement	.835***
Area 2: Digital Resources	.811***
Area 3: Teaching and Learning	.988***
Area 4: Assessment	.865***
Area 5: Empowering Learners	.948***
Area 6: Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	.908***

Note. λ = standardised factor loading*** $p < .001$. In italics the seven items specifically developed for the VET context.

3.2. Correlations between the study variables

Bivariate correlations among the study variables are reported in Table 4. All the variables were positively correlated in the directions that

Table 4
Bivariate Pearson correlation coefficients.

	1	2	3
1. PU	–		
2. PEU	.406***		
3. BI	.509***	.343***	
4. TDCB	.353***	.581***	.358***

Note. PU = Perceived Usefulness; PEU = Perceived Ease of Use; BI = Behavioural Intention; TDCB = Teachers' Digital Competence Belief. N = 2'011; *** correlation is significant at level $p < .001$.

supported the hypotheses of the study. Correlation coefficients between the study variables as well as gender, age, and teaching experience were considered negligible since they were lower than $|0.25|$, excluding the possibility that teachers' demographic characteristics could undermine the structural equation model results.

3.3. The TAM in vocational education

To assess the TAM's fitness in explaining the variance of teachers' intention to use technology within the context of vocational education (HI), we tested the relationships between PEU, PU, and BI based on the original TAM (see Fig. 1) on a sample of 2'011 teachers from Swiss vocational institutions.

As the assumption of multivariate normality was violated (Mardia's normalised coefficient Test $p < .001$), we adopted maximum likelihood estimation with robust standard errors and a Satorra-Bentler scaled test statistic. Following the modification indices, we added residual correlations between two items of the PU latent factor ($r = 0.820$, $se = 0.045$, $p < .001$). According to Byrne's (2016) recommendations, the model resulted in a good fit to the data ($\chi^2(28) = 5789.013$, $p < .001$, CFI = 0.993, TLI = 0.987, RMSEA = 0.42, SRMR = 0.020). The model explains the 37.4% variance in BI, and 73.4% in PU. Results are presented in Table 5.

3.4. TDCB as a predictor of technology acceptance

To verify the second hypothesis, we tested an extended model of TAM 1a where the TDCB is correlated with PU, PEU, and BI (see Fig. 2). A structural equation model was conducted with a maximum likelihood estimation with robust standard errors and a Satorra-Bentler scaled test statistic. Although the χ^2 statistic was associated with a significant probability value ($\chi^2(560) = 2055.035$, $p < .001$), the other fit indices indicated that the model fit the data reasonably well (CFI = 0.960, TLI = 0.955, RMSEA = 0.039, SRMR = 0.035). TDCB significantly and positively relates with PU ($b = 0.452$, $SE = 0.072$, $\beta = 0.264$, $p < .001$), PEU ($b = 1.461$, $SE = 0.057$, $\beta = 0.608$, $p < .001$), and BI ($b = 0.224$, $SE = 0.082$, $\beta = 0.105$, $p = .006$). After adding the TDCB variable in the model, the statistical significance of all the other paths between the TAM variables remain unvaried. The relationships between PEU and PU ($b = 0.252$, $SE = 0.030$, $\beta = 0.354$) and between PU and BI ($b = 0.941$, $SE = 0.063$, $\beta = 0.753$) are still positive and significant at $p < .001$.

All the significant standardised coefficients are displayed in Fig. 3.

Table 5
Results of the TAM.

Direct effects	b	SE	β	p
PEU → PU	0.366	.021	.515	<.001
PEU → BI	0.019	.032	.022	.548
PU → BI	0.971	.060	.780	<.001

Note. PU = Perceived Usefulness; PEU = Perceived Ease of Use; BI = Behavioural Intention.

Fig. 3. Results of the final model. *Note.* TDCB = Teachers' Digital Competence Beliefs; PU = Perceived Usefulness; PEU = Perceived Ease of Use; BI = Behavioural Intention. All significant standardised path coefficients between latent variables and the variances explained of the endogenous variables are displayed. A dotted line displays a non-significant path. The measurement models are not displayed.

4. Discussion

The application of the TAM to address teachers' intention to use technology for vocational education has not been sufficiently explored so far; therefore, this was the first aim of this study. The results of our analysis reveal that the TAM fits well in the context of Swiss vocational schools, and it explains a significant portion of the variance of teachers' intention to use technology in their teaching practice. The relationship between the TAM variables and the magnitude of the effects is not completely aligned with the original model (Venkatesh & Davis, 1996). Despite the fact that a direct effect of PEU on BI was hypothesised in the 1996 model, we found a non-significant correlation between these two variables. However, our result is coherent with the further elaborations of the TAM revealing that only PU directly influences BI. As the relationships between the PEU and the PU is positive and significant, PEU could be considered as an antecedent of PU, which in turn could act as a mediator between PEU and BI. These results are also consistent with Venkatesh et al. (2003), who state that among the TAM variables, PU influences intention to use technology the most. These results are also consistent with that of other studies conducted in the educational context that have found the effect on BI to be much more profound for PU than for PEU (e.g., Scherer et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2012). Thus, the strong relationship between teachers' beliefs regarding technology usefulness and their intention to use digital tools in teaching is confirmed in the context of vocational education. Our results provide further evidence of the TAM's overall reliability in the field and show that the model can be successfully applied in the context of vocational education.

Since we did not want to limit the scope of this study to validating the TAM in the vocational education context, we attempted to fill the gap in the literature regarding the relationship between TDCB and technology acceptance by testing the role of TDCB as an antecedent variable of PEU, PU and BI. To assess TDCB, we referred to the DigCompEdu framework. Although the DigCompEdu is mostly used for practice-oriented purposes—as it is intended to help teachers reflect on and understand their personal strengths and weaknesses about digital competence—it has been shown to be a good and reliable measure for research purposes as well (Ghomi & Redecker, 2019; Lucas et al., 2021; Reisoğlu & Çebi, 2020). The advantage of this measurement tool is that the items describe specific and concrete actions involving the use of technology in education and are not general items concerning the overall perception of self-efficacy in using technologies. In addition, the seven items we specifically developed and integrated in the DigCompEdu, for assessing the ability of using technology to foster the connectivity between learning locations, allow to capture the specificities of teachers' digital competence in the VET context. The confirmatory factor analysis confirms the

six-dimension structure of the TDCB scale that allowed assessing to what extent vocational teachers believe they are capable of mastering specific actions with the use of technology in their professional practice and to distinguish the level of competence perceived among the six different dimensions. A correlation between areas 1 (professional engagement) and 2 (digital resources) has been found to increase the goodness of the fit. This is consistent with the fact that these two dimensions are more related to a teacher's own professional tasks than the other four areas that progressively focus more on the pedagogical aspects of technology use and the use tools for student-centred activities.

To evaluate the relationships between TDCB and the TAM, we conducted a statistical analysis applying a structural equation model, and the overall fit of the model turned out to be good. The hypothesised positive and significant correlations between TDCB and PU, PEU and BI were confirmed (H2). The relationship between TDCB and PEU was stronger than the relationship between TDCB and PU. Indeed, it is reasonable to expect that teachers who already had a high positive belief about their digital competence considered technology to be easy to use. In addition, we interpreted the positive correlations of TDCB with PU and BI, as those beliefs about personal digital competence would lead teachers to perceive technology as useful and they would be willing to use technology in future teaching practice. Adding the TDCB variable to the model does not change the significance of the other regression paths between the TAM variables, but the regression coefficient between PU on BI in the final model is slightly lower than the same coefficient in the TAM model tested first. While from a statistical perspective this is explained by the fact that the TDCB variable captures part of the variance in BI explained by PU, for the theoretical interpretation of the relationship between TDCB and BI we returned to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB; Ajzen, 1991) as suggested by Benbasat and Barki (2007). We interpret this result as evidence that, next to PU, competence beliefs indirectly play a role in influencing behavioural intention. This explanation is coherent with TPB postulating that people's behaviour is strongly influenced by their confidence in their ability to perform it. Furthermore, TPB (Ajzen, 1991) assumes that the perception of being competent in doing something can influence beliefs related to a behaviour. Even if the perception of technology usefulness is a key determinant of the BI, we should consider the potential of TDCB in influencing the BI directly and indirectly by its effect on PU and PEU. In accordance with Backfisch et al. (2021), who found a significant direct and indirect effect of teachers' self-efficacy on technology use via technology's utility value perception, our findings reveal that teachers' beliefs about digital competence necessary to use and integrate technologies in their professional practice are significantly and positively related to the recognition of the technology usefulness, and to intention of technology use. However, the relationship between competence beliefs and usefulness beliefs is yet to be investigated further.

Overall, this study shows that teachers who perceive themselves to be competent in using educational technologies and believe that technology can enhance the teaching and learning processes are more inclined to use digital tools and software in their teaching practice than teachers with lower levels of competence and negative beliefs about technology. However, the mechanism by which digital competence beliefs influence actual technology use still needs to be investigated further.

The study contributes to extending the current perspective of the TAM as its relationship with TDCB is been examined. Scherer et al. (2019) state that “the link between the TAM and teachers' professional knowledge was missing in the primary studies, thus limiting its implications for teacher training” (p.30). We are aware that by employing a digital competence self-assessment survey instrument we have not effectively measured teachers' competence, but the beliefs that teachers have about it. However, Bandura (1986) stated that beliefs are a better predictor of future behaviours than the actual level of knowledge and skills because one's self-perception determines what people do with the competence they have.

Even if several studies have found the relationship between intention and actual behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) and although the TAM is widely validated, we recognize a significant limitation of the TAM: the behavioural intention does not always predict future behaviour (Bagozzi, 2007). Several studies on educational technology adoption have found a non-significant intention–behaviour effect (Nistor, 2014) and researchers need to be aware of the difference between the intention to use technological tools and their actual use. However, we have limited the current study to investigating the relationship between the antecedents of BI, rather than the link between BI and actual use. Indeed, as it is a cross-sectional study, we have solely assessed the relationships between TDCB, PEU and PU, and we did not measure the actual use of technology from a second timepoint, which would be a subject for future research to delve into.

Additionally, for the same reason (the cross-sectional design of the study), it is not possible to affirm that there is a causal relationship between the variables under investigation. The cross-sectional data collection allows testing the significance of the relationship between the variables and not the causality of the effects. Even if the SEM fits the data well, it does not prove the causal assumptions between the model's variables, rather it makes them more plausible (Bollen & Pearl, 2013). A longitudinal design would be necessary to investigate the causal effects of competence belief on technology acceptance, use intention and the effective use of technology by teachers.

Another limitation of this study is the non-inclusion of the affective and contextual factors that interact with an individual's cognitive beliefs. Indeed, there are several external factors that intertwine with the individual factors in hindering the enactment of a behaviour. In the current study, we focused on the original model of the TAM that encompasses the cognitive variables (i.e., PEU, PU and BI) and we investigated their relationship with another cognitive construct (i.e., TDCB). Even if the focus of the individual cognitive dimension is a limit, this is a first step to investigating the relationship between the beliefs and cognition related to technologies in vocational education. Further research is required to expand the investigation of the interaction between cognitive, emotional, and socio-contextual dimensions (i.e., institutional infrastructure, technical and educational support, digitalisation policy and organizational development) as teachers act as professionals in composite ecosystems where different factors interplay in affecting technology use (Sailer et al., 2021). Thus, it is reasonable to believe that there are other determinants that can act as external inhibitors of the behaviour that must be examined. Furthermore, since teachers come from different schools, even if the measures used in the present study refer to personal factors, the school-level differences might affect the teachers' beliefs. In our study, the low number of teacher responses for each school did not allow us to conduct a multi-level analysis. However, a multi-level data structure should be considered in future studies because the school context (e.g., the school culture, leadership, vision, etc.) partially affects the acceptance of technology and personal beliefs (Levin, 2014). Further research on the antecedents of technology acceptance and integration should use a longitudinal and multi-level design to ensure the causal relationship between variables and control for contextual factors that could enable or hinder the process of technology integration in education.

5. Conclusion

In sum, the current study confirms that the TAM can be successfully applied in the context of vocational education as well. In particular, the degree to which technology use is perceived as useful by teachers appears to be highly related to the intention to use digital tools in teaching practice. In addition, the results show that teachers' beliefs about their digital competence is positively related to their beliefs about technology usefulness in teaching, which in turn correlates with the intention to use technology. That should be considered when designing training programs that promote the use of technology for teaching and learning.

These programs should increase teachers' self-perception of digital competence through the development of teachers' digital skills and knowledge and help teachers comprehend the advantages of adopting technology to enhance teaching effectiveness and to foster the connectivity between the different vocational learning locations. The TDCB scale could be used for a preliminary assessment of the digital competence of vocational teachers to identify the areas in which teachers feel less confidence. Then, it would be possible to translate the TDCB items into specific activities that can be used to train vocational teachers to help develop their confidence in using technology. The aim is to increase communication and collaboration with all the actors of vocational education, to foster the connection between theoretical knowledge and practical skills and to enhance the connectivity between the different learning locations. In conclusion, we strongly support training teachers to help them develop their digital competence in order to increase technology acceptance and use in vocational education.

Credit author statement

Chiara Antonietti: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, **Alberto Cattaneo:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition. **Francesca Amenduni:** Writing- Reviewing and Editing.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (grant number 19-2550) and the Swiss National Science Foundation (grant number 187277).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107266>.

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